

Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intention: Case of Students at Moulay Ismail University of Meknes

Les déterminants de l'intention entrepreneuriale : cas des étudiants de l'université Moulay Ismail de Meknès

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Abstract

In recent decades, we have witnessed a proliferation of entrepreneurship education programs. In this regard, the university plays a crucial role in developing entrepreneurial skills, creativity, and innovation, thus stimulating students' entrepreneurial spirit. The objective of this article is to study the influence of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intention of students at Moulay Ismail University in Meknes. We also take into account the influence of psychological, contextual, and sociocultural factors for understanding their entrepreneurial intention comprehensively. The study of this issue draws on Shapero and Sokol's (1982) social dimensions of entrepreneurship model and Ajzen's (1991) theory of planned behavior. The chosen method involves testing a model of intention inspired by Tounès (2006). Accordingly, we analyze entrepreneurial intention, considering three sets of factors: attitudes toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The results indicate that only attitudes toward students' behavior and perceived behavioral control are significant in explaining entrepreneurial intention.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial intention; Attitude toward the behavior; Subjective norms; Perceived Behavioral Control.

Résumé

Au cours de ces dernières décennies, nous assistons à la démultiplication des formations en entrepreneuriat. En ce sens, l'université joue un rôle déterminant dans le développement des compétences entrepreneuriales, de la créativité et de l'innovation, stimulant ainsi l'esprit d'entreprendre des étudiants. À cet effet, l'objectif de cet article est d'étudier l'influence de la formation en entrepreneuriat sur l'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants de l'université Moulay Ismail de Meknès. Nous prenons également en compte l'influence des facteurs psychologiques, contextuels et socioculturels pour la compréhension de leur intention entrepreneuriale dans sa globalité. L'étude de cette problématique fait appel au modèle des dimensions sociales de l'entrepreneuriat de Shapero et Sokol (1982) ainsi qu'à la théorie du comportement planifié d'Ajzen (1991). La méthode retenue consiste au test d'un modèle d'intention inspiré de celui de Tounès (2006). Ainsi, nous analysons l'intention entrepreneuriale en prenant en compte trois ensembles de facteurs : les attitudes associées au comportement, les normes subjectives et les perceptions du contrôle comportemental. Les résultats indiquent que seules les attitudes associées au comportement des étudiants et les perceptions du contrôle comportemental sont déterminantes pour l'explication de l'intention entrepreneuriale.

Mots clé : Intention entrepreneuriale ; Attitude envers le comportement ; Normes subjectives ; Perceptions du contrôle comportemental.

Introduction

Morocco regards entrepreneurship promotion as a strategic development lever, and to this end, it has implemented a set of measures to enhance entrepreneurial culture and encourage business creation, much of which is targeted at youth. Encouraging entrepreneurial activity is of major importance in promoting employment and wealth creation to address new socio-economic needs and challenges both nationally and internationally.

Additionally, there has been a sustained increase in entrepreneurship education, programs, and training in universities, institutes, and schools. The aim is to foster an entrepreneurial culture and develop the necessary skills for realizing business creation.

Souitaris and al. (2007) assert that entrepreneurship programs positively influence subjective norms and students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. Thus, it seemed pertinent to investigate the factors that may lead students to entrepreneurial action and to explain the propensity for project creation following their education.

Many researchers share the idea that business creation is preceded by a willingness or intention to create. This intention is considered the best predictor of entrepreneurial action. Boyer (1997) suggests that intention represents the second phase after planning and precedes the decision and action to create a business. To explain entrepreneurial intention, researchers have considered various aspects such as psychological traits, personal characteristics, and entrepreneurs' cognition, and have attempted to build models for developing entrepreneurial intention (Shapero and Sokol, 1982; Kickul and Kruger, 2006).

However, these studies did not take into account external environmental factors that may affect entrepreneurial intention. It was only later that other authors (Ajzen, 1991; Shook, 2003) established an entrepreneurial intention model integrating both individual and environmental factors. Furthermore, numerous studies have sought to analyze the determinants of entrepreneurial action based on intention models. Some of these studies specifically focus on a student population in a given context.

It emerges that the three explanatory variables—attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control—have very different impacts depending on the contexts (Boissin et al., 2009). For instance, Kolvereid's (1996) study reveals that the intention to become an entrepreneur is significantly correlated with attitude, subjective norm, and perceived control. Conversely, other authors (Kennedy et al., 2003; Krueger et al., 2000) in different

geographical contexts found that only perceived desirability and feasibility are significantly correlated with the intention to choose an entrepreneurial career.

The research question at hand is:

What are the determining factors of entrepreneurial intention among students in the Moroccan university context?

In order to address this issue, we chose a quantitative study by administering a questionnaire to 190 students undergoing entrepreneurship education at three institutions within Moulay Ismail University in Meknes.

To test the conceptual model derived from our literature review, we utilized the stepwise multiple regression model. We first present the theoretical framework as the basis for our conceptual model studying the determinants of entrepreneurial action among the selected study population. The second and third sections outline the research hypotheses and the conceptual model developed. The third section describes the methodology employed. Finally, the fifth part presents the study results.

1. Literature Review

In the literature, there are several models and theories of intention. However, Shapero and Sokol's (1982) entrepreneurial event model and Ajzen's (1991) theory of planned behavior are two models that have often been used as bases in studies on the emergence of entrepreneurial intention.

The first approach is specific to the field of entrepreneurship, while the second is borrowed from social psychology. Both consider entrepreneurial intention as dependent on personal and contextual variables.

1.1. The Entrepreneurial Event Model (Shapero and Sokol, 1982)

Shapero's model (1975; Shapero and Sokol, 1982) aims to study the factors influencing the choice of entrepreneurship over other career alternatives.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the authors explain entrepreneurial action through three groups of factors: negative displacements (divorce, emigration, or dismissal), intermediate situations (leaving the military, school, or prison), and positive displacements (family influence, market existence). In connection with these factors, the authors highlight two groups of intermediate variables: perceived desirability and feasibility.

Perceived desirability refers to social and cultural variables that affect individuals' value systems. Perceived feasibility depends on factors supporting creation, such as the availability of financial and informational resources. Skills acquired through education also influence perceived feasibility.

Figure 1 : The entrepreneurial Event Theory

Source: Shapero & Sokol (1982), p.83

1.2. The Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991)

Ajzen's theory provides a reference model applicable to any intentional behavior. This intention is determined through three antecedents: attitude, subjective norm, and perceived control. Attitude toward the behavior refers to the favorable or unfavorable evaluation that individuals make of the intended behavior.

This involves considering the expected outcomes of the behavior. Perceived subjective norm refers to the social pressure exerted by close associates (parents, family, friends) to perform or not perform a behavior. Perceived control, integrated later, allowed the transition from the theory of reasoned action to the theory of planned behavior.

This variable refers to an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing a specific behavior, taking into account resources and obstacles.

Figure 2 : Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior

Source : Ajzen (1991), p.182

Thus, as shown in Figure 2, Ajzen's model posits that the more control a person has over their entrepreneurial behavior, the greater their intention will be, and the higher the likelihood of entrepreneurial action.

Furthermore, other authors such as Kolyereid (1996), Tkachev et al. (1999), Saleh (2011), Tounès (2003), Boissin et al. (2009), and Sadgui et al. (2016) have drawn inspiration from Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (1991) to study students' entrepreneurial intentions.

Several authors (Krueger et al., 2000; Emin, 2003; Tounès, 2003; Linàn, 2004; Fayolle and Gailly, 2004; Iakovleva and Kolvereid, 2009) have found empirical similarities between the entrepreneurial event model and the theory of behavior.

In fact, the notions of "perceived behavioral control" and "attitude" from the theory of planned behavior can be respectively assimilated to the notions of "feasibility" and "desirability" of the entrepreneurial event model. These studies specifically focus on students' entrepreneurial intention. We align with this line of thought by considering both approaches from a complementary perspective.

2. Research Hypotheses

In light of the main explanatory variables identified from previously developed theoretical models, we formulate our research hypotheses and the model chosen to capture the entrepreneurial intentions of students at Moulay Ismail University in Meknes. Thus, we identify three groups of factors: attitude (desirability), subjective norms, and behavioral control (feasibility).

2.1. Attitude toward the Behavior

According to Ajzen (1991), attitude is an important explanatory antecedent for understanding intention.

Several authors (Krueger et al., 2000; Vesalainen and Pihkala, 1999) agree that intention is influenced by the existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project. Tounès (2006) also asserts that the existence of a business idea, coupled with the effort to investigate certain aspects related to this idea (market, workforce needs, financial requirements, etc.), positively affects entrepreneurial intentions. Hence, the formulation of these two hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: The existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project positively affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 2: Involvement in seeking information related to the idea or project positively affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

2.2. Subjective Norms

Subjective norms or social norms concern how we perceive the ideas of other individuals (family, friends, and colleagues) about a specific behavior.

According to Maisonneuve (1971, cited by Tounès, 2003), every individual member of a group is subject to the influence of collective models and aligns with certain explicit or implicit norms by conforming to what is expected of them.

Given the literature, we acknowledge the influence of four variables on entrepreneurial intention: the existence of entrepreneur models, propensity for risk-taking, need for autonomy, and need for achievement, which are widely recognized as antecedents to entrepreneurial intention.

- The existence of entrepreneur models: young people from entrepreneurial families would be more inclined to undertake (Sénicourt and Verstraete, 2000), due to the transfer of the entrepreneurial spirit, entrepreneurial vocation, qualities, and skills necessary to enter the entrepreneurial career (Pailot, 2000):

Hypothesis 3 : Entrepreneur models positively influences students' entrepreneurial intention.

- Das and Teng (1997) argue that it is quite normal for entrepreneurs to have a very high level of risk tolerance, or even a preference for risk. Indeed, individuals with a high-risk tolerance are those most predisposed to engage in an entrepreneurial career than those with risk aversion (Janasz, Pillis, et Reardon, 2007). In line with (Tounès, 2006), we establish the following hypothesis :

Hypothesis 4: Propensity for risk-taking positively influences students' entrepreneurial intention.

- Several authors (Autio et al., 1997; Douglas, 1999; and Tounès, 2006) assert that the pursuit of autonomy is a precursor to entrepreneurial intention.

Thus, we retain the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5: The need for autonomy positively influences students' entrepreneurial intention.

According to Maslow (1943, 1954), the need for achievement or self-realization is the pinnacle of human needs.

More specifically in the field of entrepreneurship, the work of McClelland (1961) considers the need for achievement as the strongest psychological motivation associated with entrepreneurs.

Thus, the following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis 6: The need for achievement positively influences students' entrepreneurial intention.

2.3. Perceived Behavioral Control

Perceptions of behavioral control consist of perceptions of entrepreneurial abilities and perceptions of environmental resources.

On one hand, entrepreneurial training intensifies students' perceptions of their entrepreneurial abilities (Krueger and Carsrud, 1993).

On the other hand, their perceptions regarding access to information, advice, and finances to develop their projects can either positively or negatively affect their intention.

Based on the above, we formulate the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 7: Entrepreneurship or business creation specialization or support programs and training positively influence students' entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 8: The availability of resources, information, advice, and financing has a positive effect on students' entrepreneurial intention.

3. Conceptual Model

Through the hypotheses formulated, we develop our conceptual model adapted to our research work inspired by that of Tounès (2006).

Figure 3. Conceptuel Model

Source : Inspired by Tounès (2006)

4. Methodology

The objective of this article is to study the influence of a set of factors on entrepreneurial intention. We opted for a quantitative approach with a hypothetico-deductive reasoning mode, through a self-administered questionnaire survey. We opted for non-probabilistic (purposive) sampling method. We targeted three establishments of Moulay Ismail University of Meknes, namely the Faculty of Legal, Economic, and Social Sciences (FSJES), the National School of Commerce and Management (ENCG), and the Higher School of Technology (EST). These three establishments are reputed to be heavily involved in promoting entrepreneurial spirit among their students.

The target population consists of students in the final year of their bachelor's or master's degree, totaling 220 students, who have taken entrepreneurship courses during the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year.

This choice is justified by the fact that students in their final year of study already have a clear idea about their career choice. As for the response rate, it was estimated at 0.86 since the rate of usable questionnaires was 190 out of 220 distributed.

Our sample is distributed as follows:

Figure 4: Distribution of the sample by institution

Source : Authors

The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure its ease of understanding by respondents. The adjustments made following this step were very minimal. It consists of five groups of questions focusing on three groups of explanatory variables (eight hypotheses) and a single dependent variable, which is entrepreneurial intention.

These variables were measured using Likert scales with four points ranging from, for example, "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

We used items established by Kolvereid (1996), Emin (2003), Tounès (2006), Boissin et al. (2006) to measure the independent variables.

We employed the stepwise multiple regression model to determine the variables that have a significant effect on entrepreneurial intention. .

This method was chosen because it allows for determining the order of entry of variables into the model by creating variable blocks that are hierarchically entered into the model. This enables us to observe in more detail how our entrepreneurial intention model behaves.

All variables added or removed are chosen based on the test statistics of the estimated coefficient. Data analysis was conducted using the statistical software SPSS.

5. Results

The table 1 includes the descriptive statistics of our sample. Our study sample (N= 190) consists of 55.2% male students (n=105) and 44.8% female students (n=85).

Regarding age, the majority of respondents, 60.5%, belong to the age group of 20-25 years, followed by 31.6% for the age group of 26-29 years, and in third position are those over 30, with only 7.90%.

Table 1 : Descriptive Statistics for Demographic Variables

Variable	Levels	df	f	%
Gender	Male	1	105	55.2
	Female		85	44.8
Age	20-25 yrs	3	115	60.5
	26-29 yrs		60	31.6
	30 and above		15	7.90

N=190, No missing data

Source : Authors

Table 2 includes the variables specified in our study. As shown by the values of r and p, all the variables were significantly correlated to entrepreneurial intention.

**Table 2 : Relations of entrepreneurial intentions to theoritical constructs
Pearson product-moment correlations and significance probabilities**

Theoritical constructs	r	p
Attitude toward the behavior		
1 Existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project	0.533	<0.0001**
2 Involvement in seeking information	0.525	<0.0001**
Subjective norms		
3 Entrepreneur models	0.245	<0.0001**
4 Risk-taken propensity	0.152	0.009**
5 Need for autonomy	0.113	0.003
6 Need for achievement	0.236	0.004**
Perceveid Behavioral Control		
7 Entrepreneurship training	0.582	<0.0001**
8 Resource Availability	0.513	<0.0001**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Sources : Authors

Below, in Table 3, we will present the four significant models obtained following the stepwise procedure.

We notice that the first model is the most significant with ($F = 111.128$; $df = 1$ and $p = < 0.0001$).

We also observe that this first model has a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial intentions with ($\beta_1 = 0,582$; $t = 10.255$ and $p = < 0.0001$). There is no multicollinearity noted

in this model since the tolerance was > 0.1 and the variance inflation factor $VIF < 10$. Thus, the obtained model is:

$$(1) \textit{Entrepreneurship Intention} = 3.486 + 0,582 (\textit{Entrepreneurship training}) + \textit{residual } \mathcal{E}$$

In the second model, we integrated «existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project»; which produced a significant model ($F = 84.464$; $df = 2$ and $p = 0.0001$). Multicollinearity does not exist in this second regression model as tolerance was > 0.1 and the variance inflation factor $VIF < 10$ for the significant variable (existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project). The estimations of standardized coefficients show that the variables «entrepreneurship training»; and «existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project»; have a significantly positive effect on entrepreneurial intention, with coefficients respectively: $\beta_1 = 0,396$; $p < 0,0001$ and $\beta_2 = 0,374$; $p < 0,0001$.

In consequence, the standardized regression equation of entrepreneurial intentions is:

$$(2) \textit{Entrepreneurial Intention} = 3.486 + 0,380 (\textit{Entrepreneurship training}) + 0,348 (\textit{Existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project}) + \textit{residual } \mathcal{E}$$

The third model integrates the variable «involvement in seeking information»; into the regression model. The results show that this model is significant with the following values ($F = 61.171$; $p < 0,0001$). The estimations of standardized coefficients show that the three variables «Entrepreneurship training»; $\beta_1 = 0,359$; $t = 6.199$; $p < 0,0001$, «existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project»; $\beta_2 = 0,365$; $t = 4.201$; $p < 0,0001$ and «involvement in seeking information»; with $\beta_3 = 0,348$; $t = 4.605$; $p < 0,0001$; have a significantly positive effect on entrepreneurial intention.

So, the standardized regression equation of entrepreneurial intentions is:

$$(3) \textit{Entrepreneurial Intention} = 3.486 + 0,339 (\textit{Entrepreneurship training}) + 0,329 (\textit{Existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project}) + 0,321 (\textit{Involvement in seeking information}) + \textit{residual } \mathcal{E}.$$

In the last model, we integrated the variable «resource availability»; into the regression model. The obtained results also show that this model is significant with the following values ($F = 56.145$; $p < 0.001$). The estimations of standardized coefficients of the four variables taken into account reveal that they have a significantly positive effect on entrepreneurial intention.

The parameter estimates show that the four predictor variables « entrepreneurship training » with $\beta_1 = 0,353$; $t = 6.122$; $p = < 0,0001$, «existence of an idea or a more or less formalized Project » with $\beta_2 = 0,331$; $t = 4.017$; $p = < 0,0001$, « involvement in seeking information » with $\beta_3 = 0,368$; $t = 4.303$; $p = < 0,0001$, and « resource availability » with $\beta_4 = 0.143$; $t = 1.832$; $p = 0.009$; have a positively significant effect on entrepreneurial intention. The final obtained model is:

$$(4) \text{ Entrepreneurial Intention} = 3.486 + 0,332 (\text{Entrepreneurship training}) + 0,309 (\text{Existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project}) + 0,359 (\text{Involvement in seeking information}) + 0,103 (\text{Resource availability}) + \text{residual } \mathcal{E}.$$

Table 3. Parameter Estimates

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig. (p)	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tol	VIF
1 (Constant)	3.486	0,044		80.682	.000*		
Entrepreneurship training	0,453	0,044	0,582	10.255	.000*	1.000	1.000
2(Constant)	3.486	0,042		86.167	.000*		
Entrepreneurship training	0,380	0,047	0,396	6.725	.000*	0,792	1.276
Existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project	0,348	0,047	0,374	6.235	.000*	0,792	1.276
3(Constant)	3.486	0,041		85.117	.000*		
Entrepreneurship training	0,339	0,046	0,359	6.159	.000*	0,788	1.281
Existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project	0,329	0,047	0,365	4.201	.000*	0,769	1.286
Involvement in seeking information	0,321	0,046	0,348	4.605	.000*		1.309
4(Constant)	3.486	0,040		83.516	.000*	0,758	
Entrepreneurship training	0,332	0,042	0,353	6.122	.000*	0,764	1.293
Existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project	0,309	0,047	0,331	4.017	.000*	0,749	1.312
Involvement in seeking information	0,359	0,046	0,368	4.303	.000*	0,736	1.321
Resource Availability	0,103	0,042	0,143	1.832	.009*	0,947	1.048

*Significant effect.

Source : Authors

As shown in Table 4 below, the models of entrepreneurs, risk-taking propensity, need for autonomy, and need for achievement were excluded from the conceptual model.

Table 4. Excluded Variables

Model	Beta in	T	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics		
					Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance
Entrepreneur models	-0,027	-0,689	0,745	-0,017	0,756	1.373	0,832
Risk-taken propensity	-0,088	-0,118	0,578	-0,109	0,832	1.229	0,812
Need of autonomy	-0,015	-0,816	0,097	-0,032	0,785	1.361	0,801
Need for achievement	-0,091	-1.812	0,923	-0,008	0,726	1.389	0,795

Source : Authors

So the results on the effects of the main variables studied on entrepreneurial intention are included in the annotated conceptual model below:

Figure 4. Annotated Conceptual Model

Source : Authors

Figure 4 above shows that :

Attitude toward the behavior significantly affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 1 The existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 2 : Involvement in seeking information significantly affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

Subjective norms does not significantly affect students entrepreneurial intention

Hypothesis 3 : The entrepreneur model does not significantly affect students entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 4 : Risk-taken propensity does not significantly affect students entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 5 : Need for autonomy does not significantly affect students entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 6 : Need for achievement does not significantly affect students entrepreneurial intention.

Perceived Behavioral Control significantly affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 7 : Entrepreneurship training significantly affects students' entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 8 : Resource availability significantly affects students' entrepreneurial.

In Table 5, at each step, an additional explanatory variable was added to the model, and the change in R² was noted. A hypothesis test using the F-test was also performed to see if the change in R² is significant after the addition of each construct.

Table 5. Hierarchical regression analyses

Variables	Intrepreneurial Intentions					
	F	FΔ	R ² .	R ² .Δ	Df2	Sig. FΔ
Entrepreneurship training	111.128*		0,292*	0,292*	292	<0,0001*
Existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project		2.898	0,298	0,006	291	<0,0001*
Entrepreneurs model		42.236	0,369	0.076	290	0,536
Risk-taken propensity		0,406	0,370	0.001	289	0,552
Need for autonomy		0,381	0,381	0.001	289	0,572
Need for achievement		6.876	0,381	0.001	289	0,549
Involvement in seeking information		0,327	0,395	0.015	289	<0,0001*
Resource Availability		0,329	0,381	0.001	289	<0,009*

*Significant change in the amount of variation of dependent variable

Source : Authors

Table 5 shows that entrepreneurial training explains 29.2% of the variation in the dependent variables ($R^2 = 0.292$). Coupled with the existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project, the result of this model explains 29.8% of the variation in entrepreneurial intention. We have ($\Delta R^2 = 0,006$, $\Delta F = 2.898$, $\text{sig.}\Delta F = <0,0001$), which means that the integration of the variable « existence of an idea or a more or less formalized project » has a significant effect on the entrepreneurial intention model. Likewise for the Involvement in seeking information the values are ($\Delta R^2 = 0,015$, $\Delta F = 0.327$, $\text{sig.}\Delta F = <0,0001$) which explains our model to the the extent of 39.5%.

Finally, the integration of the independent variable « resource availability » has also a significant effect on our model of entrepreneurial intention with the values of ($\Delta R^2 = 0.001$ and $\Delta F = 0.329$, $\text{sig.}\Delta F = 0.009$) and explains it to the extent of 32.9%.

In summary of the results obtained from this research, only the hypotheses related to attitude toward the behavior (the existence of a more or less formalized business idea or project, involvement in seeking information) and perceived behavioral control (entrepreneurship training, resource availability) were validated. On the other hand, the hypotheses related to subjective norms (entrepreneur models, risk-taking propensity, need for autonomy, need for achievement) are not supported in this study.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study has shed light on the determinants of entrepreneurial intention in the student context, particularly the attitudes associated with entrepreneurial behavior and perceptions of behavioral control.

We have also demonstrated the impact of entrepreneurship training on the formation of entrepreneurial intention. Indeed, our results are in line with the work of several researchers (Fayolle, 2002 et al., 2006; Tkachev and Kolvereid, 1999), who have shown significant differences between students who have taken entrepreneurship courses and those who have not.

The conclusions of Hattab (2014) and Maresch et al. (2016) also highlight a direct relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions, specifying that students in business fields can benefit more from entrepreneurship education than those in engineering disciplines.

Thus, the importance of the training variable in predicting entrepreneurial intention should prompt Moroccan universities to design training and support programs to enable students to

master the process of business creation and the associated risks. We have also confirmed that the existence of a more or less formalized idea or project is a predictor of entrepreneurial intention as anticipated (Krueger et al., op.cit).

The study contributes theoretically to the research literature on educational entrepreneurship, which will help higher education institutions determine the factors that stimulate students' intentions to start a business.

On a managerial level, a major implication is that Moroccan public authorities can rely on universities to promote youth entrepreneurship. In this regard, entrepreneurship education must not only provide the necessary skills but also make entrepreneurship a desirable career choice for students. Much effort is still needed in this direction as there is often a gap between the intention to start a business and actual entrepreneurial action. Universities are called to innovate pedagogically, while public authorities must implement support measures to help young people realize their business creation projects.

However, our results show that the effect of subjective or social norms is not significant on the entrepreneurial intention of students in our sample.

Like any research, this one is not without limitations, and these limitations represent potential research avenues. As Tounès (2006) pointed out, the study of entrepreneurial intentions presents a temporal gap between the moment when students reveal their entrepreneurial intention and the moment when they carry out the act of creation.

Therefore, in order to address this limitation, it is necessary to conduct a longitudinal study in the coming years to take into account the actions carried out by students.

Finally, it seems pertinent to question the empirical link between certain educational components (course content, pedagogical methods used, profile of trainers, etc.) and the predictors of entrepreneurial intention previously identified in the entrepreneurship literature.

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